

Confidential

Date: 31/03/2022

Employer name: Quarphix

To whom it may concern

Salary Switch Request Letter

I hereby request that you update my salary deposit account to my new Absa Bank account as stipulated below:

Employee name
Your reference number
Salary deposit date (dd/mm/ccyy) (Due date)

Account details	New account	Old/Current account
Bank name	Absa Bank	ABSA bank
Branch code	632005	632005
Account number	9370631394	9370631394
Account type	SAVINGS	SAVINGS

If there are any further enquiries regarding this correspondence, contact me as your employee.

I trust that you will find the above in order.

Client full name(s) and surname